

Data management plan (DMP)

Pushing the Fundamentals of Mechanical Composite

Recycling

FuMCoRe

Version	Effective date	Description of document/changes
1.0	26.01.2026	First version of the DMP – created for the start of the project

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FWF Data Management Plan (DMP)

I General Information																											
I.1 Administrative information	<p>PI: Umut Cakmak, ORCID iD: 0000-0002-2126-6612, Johannes Kepler University of Linz, Principal Investigator</p> <p>FWF project number:</p> <p>Internal Project ID:</p> <p>DMP version: 1.0/ 26.01.2026</p> <p>Contributors: Carina Emminger, Andreas Kapshammer</p>																										
I.2 Data management responsibilities and resources	<p>Person responsible for data management and DMP: Umut Cakmak, ORCID: 0000-0002-2126-6612, Johannes Kepler University of Linz</p> <p>Co-ordination of data management responsibilities across partners: Umut Cakmak, ORCID: 0000-0002-2126-6612, Johannes Kepler University of Linz</p> <p>Resources costed in for RDM: There are no costs dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR.</p>																										
II Data Characteristics																											
II.1 Data description and collection or re-use of existing data	<p>Produced datasets:</p> <table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse; margin-top: 10px;"> <thead> <tr style="color: #4F81BD;"> <th style="width: 10%;">dataset ID</th> <th style="width: 20%;">title</th> <th style="width: 15%;">type</th> <th style="width: 15%;">format</th> <th style="width: 15%;">estimated volume</th> <th style="width: 10%;">contains sensitive data</th> <th style="width: 25%;">description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td style="text-align: center;">P1</td> <td>Documentation and reports</td> <td>Standard office documents</td> <td>pdf, docs, pptx</td> <td style="text-align: center;">20 - 50 GB</td> <td style="text-align: center;">no</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td style="text-align: center;">P2</td> <td>Experimental test data from mechanical characterization</td> <td>Raw data</td> <td></td> <td style="text-align: center;">1 - 5 TB</td> <td style="text-align: center;">no</td> <td></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>						dataset ID	title	type	format	estimated volume	contains sensitive data	description	P1	Documentation and reports	Standard office documents	pdf, docs, pptx	20 - 50 GB	no		P2	Experimental test data from mechanical characterization	Raw data		1 - 5 TB	no	
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P1	Documentation and reports	Standard office documents	pdf, docs, pptx	20 - 50 GB	no																						
P2	Experimental test data from mechanical characterization	Raw data		1 - 5 TB	no																						

P3	Image and video data from experiments, specimen preparation, and for documentation	Images, Audiovisual data		1 - 5 TB	no	
P4	Computational modeling results	Plain text		100 - 500 GB	no	

Reused datasets:

dataset ID	title	source	rights (e.g. license)	contains sensitive data	description
R1	Paper_Characterization and Modeling of Ply/Tool and Ply/Ply Slippage Phenomena of Unidirectional Polycarbonate CF Tapes	https://doi.org/10.3390/polym15173520	CC-BY-4.0	no	...
R2	Paper_Interface Characterization of Consolidated PPGF Tapes on PPGF Mat Material	https://doi.org/10.3390/polym15040935	CC-BY-4.0	no	...
R3	Paper_Application of a novel testing device to characterize the layer adhesion of co-extruded polymer sheets	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matpr.2022.05.140	CC-BY-4.0	no	...
R4	FFG-Project_Carbobrake	https://projekte.ffg.at/projekt/4206144	CC-BY-4.0	no	...

Methods and software used for data generation and reuse

Experimental test data will be generated by the material characterization with the existing equipment of the project partners IPPE and THD. Softwares for the evaluation and data processing will be Origin Pro and Microsoft Excel. For the molecular dynamics simulations the software Jocta is required.

III Documentation and Data Quality	
III.1 Metadata and documentation	<p>Data organisation, metadata, and documentation:</p> <p>The respective work package leader will handle the structure and versioning of the research data.</p> <p>As there are no domain specific metadata standards applicable, we will provide a README file with an explanation of all values and terms used at project level. This will help others to identify, discover and reuse our data.</p> <p>Additionally, we will provide common metadata such as title, description, or keywords when publishing data in open access repositories. In such a case, we will follow the default template provided by the repository.</p> <p>As far as possible, we will use controlled vocabularies for our data to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability and machine-actionability.</p> <p>Extensive documentation including methodology, experimental conditions, and limitations will be provided.</p>
III.2 Data quality control	<p>Data quality control:</p> <p>The following data quality checks will be done: calibration, repeated samples or measurements and standardised data capture.</p>
IV Data Storage, Sharing, and Long-Term Preservation	
IV.1 Data storage and backup during the research process	<p>Storage and backup facilities:</p> <p>For the duration of the project, storage and backup of data will be ensured by Carina Emminger (acting as the person responsible for data management and DMP) in cooperation with the system operator. The data will be stored on the servers of our institution.</p> <p>P3 (Image and video data from experiments, specimen preparation, and for documentation), P1 (Documentation and reports), P2 (Experimental test data from mechanical characterization), P4 (Computational modeling results), R1 (Paper_Characterization and Modeling of Ply/Tool and Ply/Ply Slippage Phenomena of Unidirectional Polycarbonate CF Tapes), R2 (Paper_Interface Characterization of Consolidated PPGF Tapes on PPGF Mat Material), R3 (Paper_Application of a novel testing device to characterize the layer adhesion of co-extruded polymer sheets), R4 (FFG-Project_Carbobrake) will be stored on IPPE Internal Server.</p> <p>P3 (Image and video data from experiments, specimen preparation, and for documentation), P1 (Documentation and reports), P2 (Experimental test data from mechanical characterization), P4 (Computational modeling results) will be stored on JKU Drive Folder.</p> <p>Data security and protection of sensitive data:</p> <p>We pay strict attention to compliance with the relevant institutional and national data protection policies. At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any sensitive data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at our institution, and the DMP will be updated.</p> <p>Access to data during research:</p>

dataset ID	selected project members	all other project members	the public
P1	writing	reading only	no access
P2	writing	reading only	no access
P3	writing	reading only	no access
P4	writing	reading only	no access
R1	reading only	reading only	reading only
R2	reading only	reading only	reading only
R3	reading only	reading only	reading only
R4	reading only	reading only	reading only

All incidents will be handled individually by an incident response team that is maintaining the affected service.

IV.2 Data sharing and long-term preservation

Data publication and access conditions:
 As far as possible, obtained datasets will be published in repositories. Details on access conditions, reuse licenses, reasons for restrictions, etc. are collected in the table below.

dataset ID	access conditions	estimated publication date	location for publication (repository)	PID	license
P1	Open	2029-01-02	Zenodo	DOI	CC-BY-4.0
P2	Open	2029-01-02	Zenodo	DOI	CC-BY-4.0
P3	Open	2029-01-02	Zenodo	DOI	CC-BY-4.0
P4	Open	2029-01-02	Zenodo	DOI	CC-BY-4.0

Repository description:

ZENODO builds and operates a simple and innovative service that enables researchers, scientists, EU projects and institutions to share and showcase multidisciplinary research results (data and publications) that are not part of the existing institutional or subject-based repositories of the research communities. ZENODO enables researchers, scientists, EU projects and institutions to: easily share the long tail of small research results in a wide variety of formats including text, spreadsheets, audio, video, and images across all fields of science. display their research results and get credited by making the research results citable and integrate them into existing reporting lines to funding agencies like the European Commission. easily access and reuse shared research results. <https://zenodo.org/>

Methods or software needed to access and use data: Potential users may need specific tools depending on the type of dataset provided. Standard experimental measurement data (e.g., mechanical test results) can typically be accessed and reused using common file formats and general analysis software. Microscopy or other image-based datasets may require dedicated image-processing software (e.g., ImageJ or vendor-specific tools) for quantitative evaluation. For simulation-related outputs (e.g., cohesive-zone or finite-element model data and calibrated parameter sets) users will likely require compatible finite-element software to reproduce, validate, or adapt the models, and for included molecular-dynamics inputs/outputs, domain-specific MD codes and scripts may be necessary. For LCA-related datasets, reuse may require standard LCA software and access to relevant databases to replicate calculations and compare scenarios.

Long-term preservation and deletion of data:

dataset ID	location for long-term storage	minimum retention period (≥ 10 years)	foreseeable research uses and/or users
P1	Zenodo	10 years	The primary target audience are researchers and engineers in composites, polymers, and recycling who work on mechanical recycling of fiber-reinforced polymers and need validated data on material degradation and interface behavior. Potential re-users include: *Composite recycling and sustainability researchers *Simulation or model developers *Material producers and suppliers
P2	Zenodo	10 years	
P3	Zenodo	10 years	
P4	Zenodo	10 years	

<p>V.1 Legal aspects</p>	<p>Personal data:</p> <p>At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any personal data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at our institution, and the DMP will be updated.</p> <p>Intellectual property rights and rights of use:</p> <p>The following individual(s) hold rights and control access to the project data: Each work package leader has the right to manage the data generated in the work package and to control access to it.</p>
<p>V.2 Ethical aspects</p>	<p>Ethical issues:</p> <p>No particular ethical issue is foreseen with the data to be used or produced by the project. This section will be updated if issues arise.</p>